

1 **Tau protein is expressed at high levels in Alzheimer's Disease induced pluripotent stem cells.**

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6 The production of signature proteins with tendency to aggregate is a central feature of neurodegenerative
7 disease: TDP-43 in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), alpha-synuclein in Parkinson's Disease, and the
8 microtubule protein Tau in Alzheimer's disease. We measured total transcription in human induced
9 pluripotent stem cell cultures engineered to express mutations found in patients with AD. We observed
10 significant production of Tau protein upon expression of AD mutants, to an extent that surpasses the
11 majority of the transcriptome. In one culture system, amyloid beta protein was found to be expressed at
12 almost undetectable levels but strong expression of islet amyloid peptide (IAPP) was observed. The
13 mutations found in humans with Alzheimer's Disease are sufficient to activate Tau and accompany
14 expression of an amyloid species early in disease.
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Results

We measured total transcription in two induced pluripotent stem cell culture systems *in vitro* to address difficulties in studying Alzheimer's Disease biology late in disease *in vivo*: a culture system in which cortical neurons cultured for 80 days were derived from induced pluripotent stem cells engineered by CRISPR to contain a mutation in PSEN1 found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease, and a second induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPS) culture system in which neurons were derived from hiPS engineered to contain a variant of apolipoprotein E gene, APOE4, comparing total transcription to isogenic iPS containing APOE3.

Induction of tau protein (MAPT) in cortical neurons derived from induced pluripotent stem cells

GSE128343

Figure 1: Mutation of presenilin 1 (PSEN1 M146V) is sufficient to induce expression of tau protein in induced pluripotent stem cells.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4137	3.31e11	0.0471	-6.632	-0.31239	10275.24	MAPT	1849/19352	90.4

PSEN1 M146V is found in patients with early-onset Alzheimer's Disease, including an Argentine family in which 13 individuals among 4 generations were affected by familial dementia. A second mutation in PSEN1 R280A, was found in a large family in Colombia with early-onset Alzheimer's Disease. The sufficiency of PSEN1 M164V to induce production of amyloid is described in an accompanying manuscript.

We next examined a second induced pluripotent stem cell culture system in which neurons were derived from isogenic hiPS: engineered to contain either APOE3, used as a control, reference transcriptome, and the APOE4 variant of the apolipoprotein E gene found in patients with AD.

High-level production of tau in neurons derived from induced pluripotent stem cells engineered to express the APOE4 polymorphism found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease.

Figure 2: Engineered APOE4 mutation results in induction of *MAPT* (tau protein).

GSE102596

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4137	1.05E-02	0.128	-2.557559	-0.3281707	17103.41	MAPT	286/15900	98.2

We again observed induction of the microtubule associated protein tau (MAPT) when comparing neurons derived *in vitro* from isogenic induced pluripotent stem cells engineered to contain either APOE3 or APOE4, a variant found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease.

In this AD culture system, we failed to observe significant production of amyloid beta precursor protein (APP) but instead found very high expression of a second amyloidogenic species produced normally in the pancreas, islet amyloid precursor protein, encoded by IAPP. IAPP is known to possess the ability to form amyloid fibrils (be amyloidogenic).

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
3375	4.11E-03	0.961	-2.869745	-2.7574557	9.3	IAPP	181/15900	98.9

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Discussion

We described here the discovery using whole transcriptome technologies that two separate mutations found in humans with Alzheimers, an apolipoprotein variant *APOE3* and a mutation in the presenilin gene, *PSEN1* M146V, are sufficient to result in significant production of tau protein in human stem cell culture, in cells differentiated to the neuronal state from iPSC.

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Methods

We used RNA-sequencing (GSE102596 and GSE128343) to measure total transcription in neuronal cell types derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells that had been engineered to contain mutations found in patients with Alzheimer’s Disease.